

Dislocation nucleation mechanisms during nanoindentation of concentrated FeNiCr alloys: Unveiling the effects of Cr through molecular simulations

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Figure 1. Dislocations nucleated during the loading process at 1nm, 4nm (max. depth) and after unloading process for the Fe55Ni19Cr26 in a), Fe74Ni8Cr18 in b), and equiatomic FeNi in c) on the [001] crystal orientation. Atomic shear strain mapping is included to indicate the relation between dislocation nucleation and strain. The dislocation types are colored according to their Burgers vectors as: $1/2\langle 110 \rangle$ Perfect (blue), $1/6\langle 112 \rangle$ Shockley (green), $1/6\langle 110 \rangle$ Stair-rod (red), $1/3\langle 100 \rangle$ Hirth (yellow), $1/3\langle 111 \rangle$ Frank (turquoise)

Figure 2 GND visualization and pile-ups formation by MD simulation for the maximum indentation depth in a-c) and after removing the indenter tip (d-f) on the [001] orientation; plastic volume is depicted by a gray colored sphere. Dislocation types are colored according to their Burgers vectors following the color palette used in Fig. 8.

Alloy	Max Depth	Unload
FeNi		
Fe55Ni19Cr26		
Fe74Ni8Cr18		

Tab. Slip traces propagation on the [111] crystal orientation showing the effect of Cr during the nanoindentation test.